

Are you ready to scale?

With our 2 open calls, selected applicants will receive funding to join our Scaling Grounds.

Twinning Programme

Mentorship and knowledge exchanges to transfer successful solutions.

Pilots Programme

Experimental projects to overcome scaling barriers.

Keep up with ScaleDem:

- scaledem.eu
- info@scaledem.eu
- [ScaleDem](#)
- [ScaleDem project](#)

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SCALEDEM

Grounding democratic innovations for real-world impact

Funded by the European Union

ScaleDem is an initiative dedicated to scaling the most effective solutions for making democracies more inclusive

From citizen science to participatory budgets or local councils, many research and innovation actions propose solutions to enhance citizen participation. Yet, too many of these solutions remain confined to the laboratory of pilot projects, waiting to be grounded in real-world practice.

ScaleDem is looking for this missing link.

We examine 4 scaling dimensions to effectively bridge research and practices gaps:

Scaling High

How to embed innovations in institutions?

Scaling Out

How to engage more citizens?

Scaling Deep

How to root participation in cultural practices?

Scaling In

How to build capacities to secure high-quality standards?

The ScaleDem infrastructure is based on 3 pillars:

Knowledge Consolidation

Our **Theory of Scaling** uses insights from over 300 research and innovation projects to identify roads to scaling across all four dimensions.

Knowledge Translation

We foster a dynamic community of practices through our **Translation Hub**, integrating global perspectives for effective knowledge translation.

Knowledge Validation

Our **Scaling Grounds** support the real-life uptake and experimentation of solutions in diverse contexts.